

EYES HEARTS HANDS
URBAN REVOLUTION

EYES HEARTS HANDS FINAL PUBLICATION

BEST PRACTICES FOR INCLUSIVE URBAN TRANSFORMATION

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INTRODUCTION

EYES HEARTS HANDS URBAN REVOLUTION (EHHUR)

EHHUR is a European-funded project whose mission is to support cities in their transition to climate neutrality. It promotes sustainable urban transformation through co-design, social inclusion and the principles of the New European Bauhaus.

Supporting sustainable urban change

European cities face increasing pressure to deliver on climate and sustainability goals in line with European ambitions. EHHUR provides a framework to help them achieve this transition while ensuring fairness, inclusion and long-term impact.

Seven demonstrator cities

The project involves seven Lighthouse demonstrators across Denmark, Greece, Belgium, Portugal, Turkey, Croatia and Italy. These cities face diverse challenges, including energy poverty, social segregation, coal transition and the decline of historic centres. The experiences of these cities generate lessons and approaches that others can adapt.

Co-design as a foundation

At the heart of EHHUR is a participatory approach. Citizens, local businesses, cultural actors and institutions are involved as active partners in the transformation of their urban environments. This builds stronger ownership and more durable solutions.

An integrated methodology

EHHUR unites people, places and ideas: it empowers citizens to take part in decisions, connects communities through inclusive financing and drives change with green technologies and respectful design. By blending culture, heritage and creativity, it shapes cities that are sustainable, inclusive and full of life.

Building knowledge for replication

The experiences of the Lighthouse cities will generate good practices and guidelines that can be applied elsewhere in Europe. Future adopters will also benefit from a Decision Support System (DSS) tool and a capacity-building programme that combine technical options, financial tools and social innovation practices to support climate-neutral urban transitions.

FULL OF EYES, HEARTS AND HANDS: OUR UNIQUE APPROACH

The novelty of Eyes Hearts Hands lies in its unique mix of methodology, engagement and financing practices, combined with strong potential for replication across contexts. The urban revolution unfolds through three interconnected pillars – Eyes, Hearts and Hands – which together turn vision into practice and ideas into action.

EYES

AESTHETICALLY VIABLE AND SOCIALLY ACCEPTED URBAN TRANSFORMATION

This pillar drives urban transformation that is both aesthetically viable and socially accepted. By leveraging local resources, skills and traditions, it reimagines cultural heritage and infrastructure in ways that respect identity while embracing innovation.

HEARTS

INCLUSIVE AND SOCIALLY FAIR INVOLVEMENT OF LOCAL COMMUNITIES

The Heart pillar ensures that green urban transformation leaves no one behind. Building on Eyes, it focuses on fairness, equality and inclusiveness, through co-design and co-creation processes that embrace diverse socio-economic contexts. Older adults, people from underprivileged backgrounds and those with disabilities are actively included, ensuring that every voice counts in shaping the city.

HANDS

CONCRETE ENGAGEMENT ACTIONS FOR FULL SUSTAINABILITY

Hands translate vision into concrete action for full sustainability. This pillar focuses on participation that turns ideas into real outcomes, through co-design tools, pilots and engagement models tested in urban contexts. By connecting citizens' input with planning, procurement and policy, it ensures communities are not only heard but empowered. Hands also embeds maintenance, circularity and long-term accountability, making transformation practical, resilient and truly shared.

BEST PRACTICES

DISCOVER THE BEST PRACTICES FROM THE PROJECT

Explore proven approaches and inspiring examples from our Lighthouse projects. Each best practice provides practical tips to help you apply these solutions in your own context.

HOW DOES IT WORK?

Each best practice is presented over two pages and is marked with a Lighthouse flag, showing which Lighthouse it applies to. The icons – Eye, Heart and Hand – indicate which approach it best represents. Following the main description, practical “Dos and Don’ts” provide clear guidance for applying the lessons effectively.

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EMBED CO-CREATION FROM THE START

DESIGN WITH, NOT FOR

Engaging citizens, communities, and stakeholders from the earliest stages makes projects more relevant, supported, and durable. Co-creation goes beyond consultation to genuine collaboration, where lived experience meets professional expertise to design solutions that people value, use, and maintain. It also builds trust, improves transparency, and strengthens capacity for future action across communities and institutions.

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SUMMARY

EHARR's co-design process treats co-creation as a planned sequence rather than an isolated event. Start by defining what will be decided with citizens, mapping stakeholders, and selecting inclusive forums. Use iterative activities such as open calls, design charrettes, school projects, neighbourhood walks and small trials in streets or parks to test ideas. Close the loop by showing how input shaped the design, and by explaining what was not possible and why. In Kazani, school workshops and park visioning generated proposals for routes, shade, and seating that fed into the final plan. In Meis, resident participation in selecting benches and green layouts increased trust and satisfaction during housing renovation. These cases reflect MEI's Together principle: attention to local place and culture supports beautiful, durable, circular choices contribute to sustainable. Helpful enablers include small pilot budgets, plain-language materials, and cross-department teams with technical, social, and financial expertise. Keep a simple decision log to track progress from idea to implementation, and align engagement checkpoints with procurement so insights shape specifications and contracts.

3

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> DOS	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> DON'TS
1. Define shared decisions and roles	1. Run one-off events without follow-up
2. Map stakeholders led, hand-to-reach	2. Invite only the usual, vocal participants
3. Use games, walks, charrettes, online	3. Promise influence you cannot deliver
4. Publish a decision log after sessions	4. Hide trade-offs; explain constraints
5. Budget for pilots and quick trials	5. Bury people in jargon or long reports
6. Invite technical, social, finance staff	6. Separate engagement from procurement
7. Bring simple prototypes to test	7. Ignore conflicting feedback; document it

BEST PRACTICES FROM THE PROJECT 13

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6

1. Pilots affected by the best practice
2. Reference image of the best practice
3. Name of the best practice and brief summary
4. Main text and description
5. Approach used in this practice
6. Lesson learned (dos/do'n'ts)

BEST PRACTICES FOR INCLUSIVE URBAN TRANSFORMATION

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LEGEND

HOW TO READ THE FLAGS

To guide readers through the project, each lighthouse district is marked with a dedicated flag. These visual markers make it simple to trace the connection between the best practices and the places where they were developed or tested. By highlighting the relevant flags in the top-left corner of each lighthouse page, the design offers readers an immediate visual cue, ensuring that the link between practices and districts is clear and consistent throughout the book.

DENMARK, HØJE-TAASTRUP

GREECE, KOZANI

BELGIUM, ZOERSEL

PORTUGAL, MAIA

TURKEY, IZMIR

CROATIA, OSIJEK

ITALY, BIODISTRETTO

EMBED CO-CREATION FROM THE START

DESIGN WITH, NOT FOR

Engaging citizens, communities and stakeholders from the earliest stages makes projects more relevant, supported and durable. Co-creation goes beyond consultation to genuine collaboration, where lived experience meets professional expertise to design solutions that people value, use and maintain.

It also builds trust, improves transparency and strengthens capacity for future action across communities and institutions.

SUMMARY

EHHUR's co-design process treats co-creation as a planned sequence rather than an isolated event. Start by defining what will be decided with citizens, mapping stakeholders and selecting inclusive formats. Use iterative activities such as open calls, design charrettes, school projects, neighbourhood walks and small trials in streets or parks to test ideas. Close the loop by showing how input shaped the design and by explaining what was not possible and why. In Kozani, school workshops and park visioning generated proposals for routes, shade and seating that fed into the final plan. In Maia, tenant participation in selecting finishes and green layouts increased trust and satisfaction during housing renovation. These cases reflect the New European Bauhaus principles: Together, by involving citizens directly; Beautiful, by respecting local identity and culture; and Sustainable, by adopting durable and circular solutions. Key enablers include small pilot budgets, plain-language communication materials, and cross-departmental teams with technical, social, and financial expertise. A simple decision log helps track progress from idea to implementation, while aligning engagement checkpoints with procurement ensures that community input is carried through into specifications and contracts.

| DON'TS |
|--|--|
| <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Define shared decisions and roles 2. Map stakeholders incl. hard-to-reach 3. Use games, walks, charrettes, online 4. Publish a decision log after sessions 5. Budget for pilots and quick trials 6. Invite technical, social, finance staff 7. Bring simple prototypes to test | <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Run one-off events without follow-up 2. Invite only the usual, vocal participants 3. Promise influence you cannot deliver 4. Hide trade-offs; explain constraints 5. Bury people in jargon or long reports 6. Separate engagement from procurement 7. Ignore conflicting feedback; document it |

MAP STAKEHOLDERS FOR IMPACT

KNOW WHO TO INVOLVE

Thorough stakeholder mapping ensures all relevant people, groups and institutions are identified and understood early in a project. By recognising those with influence, interest, expertise or resources, cities can focus engagement where it will have the most effect. A clear process prevents blind spots, builds trust and links projects to local knowledge, lived experience and networks so that no key perspective is missed.

SUMMARY

EHHUR's co-design guidance includes a structured stakeholder mapping process to identify, categorise and prioritise those who can shape, support or be affected by a project. Stakeholders are assessed by their influence, interest and capacity to contribute, enabling tailored engagement strategies. In Maia, mapping highlighted NGOs and cultural groups already trusted by residents, leading to deeper participation. In Zoersel, it brought in municipal staff and local service providers whose practical knowledge informed procurement choices and improved long-term maintenance planning. In Kozani, schools were recognised as important connectors between the municipality and families, increasing youth and parent involvement. This practice reflects NEB's Together principle by ensuring diversity of voices, while Sustainable is supported by involving actors who can maintain, operate, or fund interventions. Effective mapping combines desk research, targeted interviews and referrals from known contacts and is updated as conditions evolve. A shared visual map improves coordination across teams, avoids duplication and clarifies each stakeholder's role and level of influence.

DOS

1. **Map influence, interest and resources**
2. **Include informal and grassroots actors**
3. **Update mapping as projects evolve**
4. **Use interviews to find hidden influencers**
5. **Share the map internally for alignment**
6. **Tailor engagement to each stakeholder type**
7. **Validate mapping with local partners**

DON'TS

1. **Focus only on formal institutions**
2. **Treat mapping as a one-time task**
3. **Exclude low-influence but high-interest groups**
4. **Assume existing lists are complete**
5. **Ignore changing priorities over time**
6. **Keep mapping results siloed**
7. **Overlook suppliers or maintenance staff**

INTEGRATE NEW EUROPEAN BAUHAUS PRINCIPLES IN DESIGN

APPLY NEW EUROPEAN BAUHAUS PRINCIPLES

Integrating the New European Bauhaus principles — Beautiful, Sustainable, Together — into every design choice ensures projects are functional, inclusive and inspiring for residents and visitors alike. This approach gives equal priority to aesthetics, environmental impact and community connection. It guides decisions on materials, forms and layouts so that places are welcoming, durable and rooted in local identity.

SUMMARY

EHHUR's design process uses the New European Bauhaus principles as a shared framework for balanced decisions from concept to delivery. Beautiful encourages designs that respect cultural heritage and enhance the character of streets, parks and buildings. Sustainable prioritises low-carbon materials, circular resource use and energy efficiency. Together ensures spaces are inclusive, accessible and shaped with community input. In Høje-Taastrup, the principles supported reuse of local materials and creation of public areas for mixed-age interaction. In Maia, they guided green courtyards and shaded walkways in renovated housing blocks. In Kozani, they informed a park plan with natural shading, native planting and community activity areas. Applying the framework early helps reveal trade-offs and inspire creative solutions. Check concepts against each principle, record decisions and explain them to stakeholders to build shared ownership. Providing visuals, mock-ups, or pilots helps residents understand and support the vision. Aligning NEB principles with local plans and procurement ensures they remain central through construction and operation.

DO'S

1. Define what Beautiful, Sustainable, Together mean locally
2. Use them in early design reviews and decisions
3. Select low-carbon, durable, circular materials
4. Balance heritage with modern needs
5. Plan for all ages and abilities
6. Test concepts with visuals or pilots
7. Record and explain design choices

DON'TS

1. Treat NEB as a slogan without action
2. Prioritise aesthetics over function or inclusion
3. Ignore embodied carbon or material impacts
4. Overlook maintenance in design decisions
5. Apply a one-size-fits-all design template
6. Leave principles out of procurement criteria
7. Skip explaining trade-offs to the public

ALIGN ENGAGEMENT WITH PROCUREMENT AND CONTRACTS

ENGAGE TO SHAPE PROCUREMENT & CONTRACTS

When engagement is aligned with procurement and contracting, community input can shape technical requirements, materials and delivery methods. This connection ensures ideas gathered in co-creation are reflected in specifications and tenders. It creates a clear route from discussion to action, improving transparency, quality and trust while reducing rework. A handover step to tender drafting makes the process repeatable.

SUMMARY

EHHUR links engagement outputs to procurement so community input informs specifications, budgets and contracts. Insights from co-design activities, pilots and stakeholder mapping are reviewed before tender documents are finalised, helping suppliers deliver solutions that match agreed priorities. In Maia, feedback on layouts and materials was translated into renovation requirements. In Zoersel, input from staff and residents supported criteria that favoured reuse and longer product lifecycles. In Høje-Taastrup, engagement results guided accessibility and green infrastructure requirements in construction contracts. The practice supports NEB's Together by giving residents a voice in binding documents; Sustainable by embedding durability and low-carbon choices in tenders; and Beautiful by aligning design quality with local identity. Key steps include timing engagement to precede procurement, summarising feedback in a format usable by technical teams and preparing procurement staff to interpret community priorities. Track the links in a simple decision log so everyone can see how ideas move from workshops to specifications and, later, to delivered outcomes. Add brief checkpoints.

DO'S

1. Plan engagement before procurement
2. Summarise feedback for technical teams
3. Translate community input into specs
4. Include NEB and lifecycle value
5. Use pilots to test options pre-tender
6. Train procurement staff to read inputs
7. Record links from feedback to clauses

DON'TS

1. Run engagement after contracts are set
2. Ignore feedback due to format
3. Omit social or environmental requirements
4. Split design work from community input
5. Let suppliers dilute agreed specs
6. Skip explaining procurement decisions
7. Fail to document how input was used

USE TEMPORARY INTERVENTIONS AS LOW-RISK PILOTS

TEST IDEAS WITH TEMPORARY PILOTS

Temporary interventions are small-scale, short-term changes that let cities test design ideas, materials, or layouts before committing to permanent investment. They provide real-world evidence on how people use and respond to a place, helping teams refine solutions and avoid costly mistakes. Pilots also build momentum and trust by showing visible action and inviting feedback on what works in daily use across user groups.

SUMMARY

EHHUR uses temporary interventions as practical trials in streets, parks, housing areas and service delivery. Pilots can include pop-up seating, planting beds, shade structures, traffic calming measures and test efficient lighting. In Kozani, a temporary park layout with shading, seating and planting tested circulation, comfort and activity areas, with feedback collected on-site and online before implementation. In Maia, small-scale green infrastructure demonstrations showed benefits, informed upkeep tasks and helped estimate costs and schedules. Pilots reduce risk, surface practical issues and support community buy-in by letting people experience options in real conditions. They align with NEB's Beautiful by enhancing the quality of place, Sustainable by testing durable and circular materials and Together by inviting diverse users to respond. To succeed, set clear aims and evaluation criteria, make participation accessible, communicate the timeframe and remove pilots on schedule. Link findings directly to procurement and design so lessons carry into permanent works and document results for cross-department learning and future replication. Share results to aid replication.

DOS

1. **Define clear aims and evaluation criteria**
2. **Design for easy setup, removal and reuse**
3. **Involve community in pilot design and review**
4. **Test multiple materials or layouts at once**
5. **Communicate that changes are temporary**
6. **Collect feedback during and after use**
7. **Share results across departments**

DON'TS

1. **Launch pilots without a learning goal**
2. **Use low-quality materials that bias results**
3. **Skip informing stakeholders of purpose**
4. **Treat pilots as permanent without review**
5. **Ignore maintenance needs during tests**
6. **Discard feedback or fail to analyse it**
7. **Keep lessons within one department**

PLAN FOR LONG-TERM MAINTENANCE AND LIFECYCLE COSTS

DESIGN FOR LIFECYCLE VALUE

Planning for maintenance and lifecycle costs from the outset helps cities design projects that are durable, affordable to operate and realistic to manage. Considering upkeep, replacement cycles and resource use alongside design choices reduces total cost of ownership and prevents underperformance over time. It also supports circular practices by prioritising repair, reuse, adaptable components and long service life.

SUMMARY

EHHUR promotes lifecycle-based planning so that maintenance, operations and replacement are considered in design and procurement. Teams assess expected service life, availability of parts, reparability, energy use and disposal routes when comparing options. Procurement criteria can reward durability, modular components and take-back schemes. In Maia, renovation planning linked material choices to maintenance tasks and schedules. In Zoersel, supplier requirements included reuse potential and service agreements. In Høje-Taastrup, public space designs reflected upkeep capacity and seasonal workload. This practice aligns with NEB's Sustainable by reducing waste and energy demand, supports Together by ensuring spaces remain safe and usable for all and contributes to Beautiful by maintaining design quality over time. Key steps include preparing a lifecycle cost model, setting maintenance standards and assigning clear responsibilities for inspection and repair. Track costs and performance in a simple register to inform future decisions and use pilot trials to validate maintenance assumptions before scaling. Share results.

DOS

1. **Prepare a lifecycle cost model early**
2. **Specify durability, reparability, spare parts**
3. **Include maintenance standards in contracts**
4. **Use modular, reusable components**
5. **Align design with available upkeep capacity**
6. **Train operations staff before handover**
7. **Track costs and performance in a register**

DON'TS

1. **Choose lowest upfront cost without lifecycle view**
2. **Specify bespoke parts that are hard to replace**
3. **Ignore access for cleaning and repairs**
4. **Separate design from maintenance planning**
5. **Overlook warranties**
6. **Delay budgets for operations and upkeep**
7. **Skip pilots that validate assumptions**

COMBINE TECHNICAL, SOCIAL AND FINANCIAL EXPERTISE

BUILD INTEGRATED PROJECT TEAMS

Urban regeneration involves complex trade-offs. Bringing technical, social and financial expertise together early helps cities design solutions that are feasible to build, inclusive for users and viable to fund and maintain. Integrated teams reduce silos, speed decisions and ensure that design choices weigh performance, affordability, maintenance and community priorities at the same time, with handovers between roles.

SUMMARY

EHHUR applies an integrated team approach so engineering, social and finance expertise work together through delivery phases. Technical staff translate community needs into specifications; social experts design inclusive engagement; finance teams align budgets, funding and lifecycle costs. In Maia, renovation planning balanced material choices, tenant needs and costs. In Kozani, planners worked with educators to support youth engagement on public space concepts. In Zoersel, operational staff and procurement worked with designers to include maintenance and reuse in criteria. This practice supports NEB's Together by coordinating disciplines, Sustainable by embedding lifecycle considerations and Beautiful by maintaining design quality. Key steps include defining roles and decision rights, scheduling joint reviews at milestones and using plain summaries so insights move between groups. Shared tools like decision logs and short cost-impact notes help teams track how input, options and constraints shape choices. Hold joint reviews and add short cost and social notes to each option to support decisions.

| DON'TS |
|--|---|
| <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Form teams with technical, social, finance roles 2. Define responsibilities and decision rights 3. Hold joint reviews at key milestones 4. Translate engagement into specifications 5. Add short cost and social notes to options 6. Align funding plans with design and phasing 7. Keep a shared decision log | <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Plan in silos without cross-discipline input 2. Leave finance or social roles until late 3. Use jargon that blocks collaboration 4. Ignore maintenance and lifecycle costs 5. Treat engagement results as separate reports 6. Change specs without updating budgets 7. Skip documenting why choices were made |

APPLY INCLUSIVE FINANCING MODELS FOR URBAN PROJECTS

BUILD SUSTAINABLE, INCLUSIVE FINANCING

Inclusive financing combines public funds, private investment and community contributions to support urban projects that deliver social and environmental value. Planning financing from the start, alongside design and engagement, helps cities select options that are affordable to deliver and sustain. This approach broadens participation, shares risk, reduces reliance on a single source and strengthens long-term stewardship.

SUMMARY

EHHUR provides guidance for building sustainable financing plans and selecting funding options matched to context. Cities can combine grants and subsidies with private capital and local contributions, aligning repayments and risk with expected benefits. A structured plan clarifies responsibilities, timelines, cash flows and monitoring so projects remain viable beyond initial investment. Deliverables include a catalogue of financing practices and a sustainable financial plan template that cities can adapt. Practical steps include mapping programmes, identifying partners and testing affordability using lifecycle costs and sensitivity checks. Procurement and contracting can reflect financing choices by rewarding durability and predictable operating costs and require transparent reporting. This practice supports NEB by linking social and environmental aims to realistic funding pathways and accountability. To maintain confidence, publish a plain-language summary of the plan, set milestones for review and track outcomes so lessons inform future projects. Review and update the plan.

DOS

DON'TS

1. **Start financial planning at concept stage**
2. **Mix public funds, private capital, local input**
3. **Map programmes and partners with timelines**
4. **Test affordability with lifecycle costs**
5. **Link financing to procurement criteria**
6. **Publish a plain-language summary**
7. **Review and update the plan at milestones**

1. **Rely on a single grant or source**
2. **Ignore operating and maintenance costs**
3. **Separate financing from design decisions**
4. **Overlook risk-sharing and contingencies**
5. **Delay partner engagement until late**
6. **Hide assumptions or cash-flow limits**
7. **Skip monitoring of financial performance**

MONITOR AND ADJUST THROUGH THE PROJECT LIFECYCLE

CONTINUOUS MONITORING AND IMPROVEMENT

Regular monitoring allows cities to track whether urban regeneration projects deliver intended benefits and to make timely adjustments. By combining technical, social and economic indicators, teams can detect issues early, share progress transparently and refine designs or operations. This approach builds accountability, supports adaptive management and ensures resources are used effectively to achieve long-term goals.

SUMMARY

EHHUR promotes monitoring as an integrated part of project delivery, not a post-completion add-on. Cities track agreed indicators for environmental performance, social outcomes and economic viability throughout design, construction and operation. Deliverables include a techno-socio-economic integration analysis method to link monitoring data to decision-making, ensuring adjustments are evidence-based and timely. In Kozani, tracking park use after initial works guided seating and shade improvements that matched resident needs. In Maia, monitoring tenant satisfaction during renovation helped address noise, dust and access issues promptly. Indicators can include energy use, comfort, biodiversity, participation rates, maintenance costs and budget control. Data should be collected at agreed intervals, analysed collaboratively by multidisciplinary teams and summarised in plain language for stakeholders. Feedback loops enable mid-course corrections, strengthen trust and help replicate successes in future projects. Archiving results and decisions creates a reference for scaling and transferring practices to other contexts. Updating indicators when conditions change ensures relevance.

DOS

1. **Agree indicators with stakeholders early**
2. **Track environmental, social, economic metrics**
3. **Collect and analyse data at set intervals**
4. **Share results in accessible formats**
5. **Use findings to adjust plans and designs**
6. **Document changes and their impacts**
7. **Integrate lessons into future projects**

DON'TS

1. **Leave monitoring until after completion**
2. **Measure only technical performance**
3. **Ignore stakeholder-defined priorities**
4. **Collect data without using it**
5. **Hide results or delay sharing**
6. **Overcomplicate with too many indicators**
7. **Fail to link monitoring to decisions**

EMBED CIRCULARITY FROM TENDER TO DELIVERY

AIM FOR CIRCULAR PROCUREMENT AND DESIGN

Circular approaches in procurement and design extend the life of materials, reduce waste and lower environmental impact. By setting clear criteria from the start, cities can influence suppliers and contractors to deliver solutions that are durable, repairable and reusable. This ensures investments support long-term sustainability, resource efficiency and the creation of value chains that benefit the local economy.

SUMMARY

EHHUR encourages embedding circularity principles from the earliest stages of procurement and design. This involves specifying durability, ease of maintenance and reuse potential in tender documents and evaluating bids not only on cost but also on lifecycle performance. Deliverables include a catalogue of best practice solutions and methods to integrate technical, social and economic considerations, ensuring circular choices are feasible and supported by stakeholders. In Zoersel, engaging maintenance staff and suppliers during procurement identified products with lower replacement needs, reducing lifecycle costs. In Maia, circular procurement supported reuse of existing elements during social housing renovation and reduced landfill waste. Key steps include mapping available circular products and suppliers, setting measurable criteria for waste reduction and tracking material flows during construction. This aligns with NEB principles by combining sustainability with functional and aesthetic quality and by fostering local value chains. Monitor supplier performance, training contractors and updating criteria as markets evolve strengthen results.

DOS

DON'TS

1. **Set circularity criteria in tenders**
2. **Engage maintenance staff in procurement**
3. **Prioritise durable, repairable materials**
4. **Evaluate lifecycle performance, not just cost**
5. **Track material flows during construction**
6. **Support local circular supply chains**
7. **Include reuse and recycling targets**

1. **Rely solely on lowest-cost bids**
2. **Ignore maintenance and replacement cycles**
3. **Specify without market research**
4. **Overlook training for circular practices**
5. **Separate circularity from other design aims**
6. **Fail to verify supplier claims**
7. **Discard reusable materials without review**

ACTIVATE UNDERUSED SPACES FOR COMMUNITY BENEFIT

BRING LIFE TO IDLE URBAN SPACES

Temporary use of idle or neglected spaces can deliver quick community benefits, test ideas and build momentum for longer-term regeneration. By involving residents in design and programming, cities can turn underused plots or buildings into valued places that meet local needs and aspirations. This approach fosters ownership, supports social cohesion, makes visible progress early and reduces risk of long-term vacancy.

SUMMARY

EHHUR promotes temporary use as a practical strategy to activate spaces while long-term plans are underway. Through low-cost, low-regret steps, cities can pilot ideas, strengthen networks and refine future investments using real-world feedback. Deliverables include methods to co-design activities with stakeholders, align them with NEB and integrate lessons into final plans. In Kozani, quick park improvements with seating, shade and play elements were tested during co-design, increasing use and informing permanent layouts. In Maia, underused housing courtyards became meeting points via resident-led gardening, cultural events and small markets. In Osijek, partnerships with Udruga Breza engaged youth in co-creating temporary uses like murals and micro-gardens, building skills and local pride. Key steps include identifying candidate sites, engaging diverse users to generate ideas, setting clear timeframes and providing basics like seating, shade and lighting. Monitoring use and feedback during activation helps retain successful elements and refine or replace weaker ones. Documenting the process helps other districts replicate and adapt. Share brief results to aid replication.

DOS

1. Identify idle sites with community potential
2. Engage residents in co-design of uses
3. Start with low-cost, reversible changes
4. Provide seating, shade, lighting and safety
5. Support local groups to run activities
6. Monitor use and gather feedback
7. Integrate lessons into permanent plans

DON'TS

1. Leave spaces unused during planning
2. Over-invest before testing ideas
3. Exclude groups from design discussions
4. Ignore basic safety and accessibility
5. Impose activities without consultation
6. Fail to communicate timeframes
7. Neglect to evaluate temporary uses

APPLY NATURE-BASED COOLING AND CLIMATE RESILIENCE

DESIGN GREEN-BLUE URBAN COOLING

Nature-based solutions use vegetation, water and natural systems to cool cities, manage water and improve quality of life. Integrating trees, green roofs, permeable surfaces and water features into streets, squares and courtyards can reduce heat, capture rain and boost biodiversity. This approach improves comfort, supports health and makes public spaces more inviting year-round while building climate resilience.

SUMMARY

EHHUR promotes nature-based solutions (NBS) as a core strategy for climate adaptation and livable cities. By embedding green-blue infrastructure into regeneration plans, cities can address heat stress, flooding and biodiversity loss while enhancing public space. Deliverables include a catalogue of NBS options, design integration methods and techno-socio-economic assessments to guide adoption. In Izmir, early-stage plans integrate tree-lined corridors, shaded seating and permeable paving to cool streets and support walking. Kozani tested small park interventions with shade trees and planted areas to lower summer temperatures. Maia transformed underused housing courtyards into green community spaces, improving comfort and social use. In Zoersel, rain gardens and permeable surfaces around civic buildings cut runoff and created habitats. Key steps include mapping urban heat islands, selecting climate-appropriate species and designing for low maintenance. Engaging communities in planting and care builds stewardship and strengthens the NEB principle of 'Together'. Monitoring performance over time ensures NBS deliver expected cooling, water retention and biodiversity gains.

DOS

1. **Map heat islands and flood-prone areas**
2. **Select native, climate-suited species**
3. **Integrate shade, water and permeable surfaces**
4. **Design for easy, low-cost maintenance**
5. **Engage community in planting and care**
6. **Combine NBS with social and cultural uses**
7. **Monitor cooling and biodiversity impacts**

DON'TS

1. **Plant species unsuited to local climate**
2. **Ignore long-term maintenance needs**
3. **Over-engineer without ecological value**
4. **Separate NBS from public space design**
5. **Miss opportunities for multifunctional use**
6. **Neglect community engagement**
7. **Fail to track performance over time**

FROM PRACTICES TO PRINCIPLES

The twelve best practices collected in this book show that the Eyes, Hearts, Hands model is not an abstract concept, but a method that drives concrete urban transformation. Each case, though rooted in different contexts, confirms that changing cities requires the interplay of three dimensions: the quality and identity of places (Eyes), the inclusion and participation of people (Hearts) and the operational and managerial tools that make change real and lasting (Hands).

WHAT WE LEARNED

Across the practices, several common lessons emerge:

The value of process:

the most successful outcomes arise when co-creation, stakeholder mapping and monitoring are integrated from the very beginning, not treated as add-ons.

Bridging social and technical dimensions:

financing, contracts and maintenance become inclusive when aligned with community needs.

Experimentation as leverage:

temporary interventions, activation of underused spaces and circular approaches allow cities to test and consolidate solutions.

The centrality of sustainable design:

aesthetics, climate resilience and lifecycle awareness are essential conditions for projects that endure over time.

LOOKING AHEAD

Taken together, the best practices confirm that Hands provide the operational backbone of almost every action, while Hearts ensure no one is left out and that solutions are genuinely shared. Eyes come into play more selectively but decisively, whenever design quality and environmental identity become key to giving projects meaning and coherence.

This combination makes the approach highly replicable: not a rigid recipe, but a flexible set of principles and tools that cities can adapt to their own challenges. The book demonstrates that urban change is possible—if we look with attentive eyes, build with competent hands and above all, keep the heart at the centre of transformation.

MAIA

ZOERSEL

HØJE-TAASTRUP

BIODISTRETTO

OSIJEK

KOZANI

IZMIR

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